

BASICS OF ADJUSTING PHYSICAL EXERCISES FOR THE AGE OF STUDENTS WHEN INTRODUCING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE TO STUDENTS IN THE GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION SYSTEM

Jurayev Vohidjon Muhammedovich

Associate professor of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute, Uzbekistan

e-mail: vohidjonjurayev423@gmail.com

Ermатов Yoqubjon

Student of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute, Uzbekistan

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Annatation: this article cites data on the implementation of physical exercises according to the age, physical development and physical fitness of students when introducing a healthy lifestyle to students in the general secondary education system.

Keywords: physical load, healthy lifestyle, agenda, tight Health, conditioned reflex, unconditional reflex, Family, School, Living tarsi.

Introduction. It is clear to all of us that regular exercise forms the healthy views of our children, young people and refreshes their will, provides a solid foundation for their maturation as brave and courageous people, for the various districts to be able to overcome trials and difficulties valiantly. Most of all, children who are friends with sports are completely alien to us and do not get involved in harmful flows. Today, in modern sports fields newly built in our cities and villages, our young people spend their free time meaningfully. Such work pays off. Our life is changing, our consciousness, our worldview is changing, our attitude towards ourselves, our own health, our future is changing, and in the process, among many other positive factors, sports are first of all greatly affected.

It is no secret to whom sport is an incomparable tool that, along with improving health, makes the world famous for which country and which country. The achievements of our athletes on international fields arouse in our hearts the feelings of the grotesque riftikhor, further elevating the feeling of love for our motherland. Sport is becoming the most important and powerful factor in the upbringing of future generations in our country, and it is no doubt that it will remain so in the future.

Main part. The STT physical culture requires the choice and planning of daily movement patterns and physical load, in accordance with its age and physical fitness. The main issue goes back to how to organize movement activities, how to engage in physical activities in order to solve the recorded requirements. It depends on the type of exercise you are choosing to practice, given their age and individual nature. Someone chooses to walk, someone to run, swim, ride a bike, go with a dumbbell, a 1-2 poodle pack with a stone, and someone else from sports games to do something of his favorite kind, etc. The physiological focus of physical exercises of the above variety of manifestations is mainly on the development of strength and endurance of the leading action qualities of the health of the body. This preparation is not limited to preparing a person for high production activities only in labor (mental, physical), but makes it easier to master vital-practical qualifications, as well as cope with difficulties in social life, overcome them and easily get out of extreme situations in peace, military conditions.

The results of the sociological survey showed that students did not have enough knowledge and qualifications necessary to choose one of the mass sports, that is, suitable for them. Students (63%) who self-identify as having a STT Physical Culture consider it important (37%) that regular involvement in some form of sport during their years of study makes it a habit (). Because the current lifestyle has claimed to take up a lot of time (40.1%) for passive (sitting) activities in them. In particular, the excess of the need for computers, computing techniques, television and others forms the basis of the current daily lifestyle. To ensure that mental and physical activity is constantly regular, as well as to promote health, constant exercise puts the problem of how to choose a suitable sport. Its solution is due to the fact that when choosing a sport, the individual's physical abilities, physical capabilities are developed, their readiness is appropriate. For example, the height is lower, the arm, neck are short wrestling, swimming, table tennis, football, sports gymnastics, boxing, tourism, chess-checkers, etc. Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.

For middle-aged people, it is good for them to practice sports such as handball, solo wrestling, volleyball, tennis, badminton, national wrestling, athletics, basketball. But this does not mean that they cannot be engaged in other types of sports. Because each person is different from each other in that he is interested, infects movement activity, welcomes him. They do not engage in the goal of achieving a high sporting result with the sports they like, or it is also possible that the goodness of the conditions for these types takes into account the good of the base, its proximity, the coach they like and others. In addition, the age of 18-24 years is the first stage of the body's maturation period, the period of large doses of loads and the possibility of energy expenditure.

During this period, it has been proven in practice that a certain level of mode of action, the formation of a habit on it, becomes a habit for a lifetime. V.D. In Chernyavsky's opinion, the following forms of Physical Culture training can be included in the weekly schedule for those who are mentally employed: morning Gymnastics (15-20 minutes), practicing wellness Gymnastics in a wellness group or independently, cyclic exercises, games (from 30-60 minutes to 2 times a week), special exercises (from 5-7 minutes to 2-3 times a week), as well as

Conclusion. The fact that a person does not rest at the time of rapid exhaustion, the family turmoil, physical and mental tension, exhaustion, mental activity that exceeds his need, a violation of his relationship with a loved one, the loss of living, working and other things that are valuable to him leads to tension disorder. constant-acting strain factors contribute to the violation of the metabolism of substances in the human body, the cranial nerve cells are pushed into the hallmark, impair memory. Reduces human capabilities and leads to disruption of activity. :- proper lifestyle, nutrition, good rest orlish, carnal education - good intentions, creative activity rest, playing a favorite sport activity - temperance, hygienic factors-physical education and playing sports lead to a proper life and living well.

For health care, it is necessary to properly regularly engage in physical education in the first place. - when educating young people in a healthy way, it is first of all necessary to form a healthy lifestyle. - it is necessary to use hygienic factors wisely to increase physical activity. - when directing the younger generation to mass sports and National Sports, It is advisable to adapt them to their age.

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